

Investigation of Studies on Romanian Rural Tourism with Bibliometric Analysis

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ABSTRACT

Rural tourism, which emerged when people struggling with stress in crowded city life went to rural areas in line with their desire to discover themselves, to be intertwined with nature and to return to their essence, offers the local people employment opportunities in many different areas. In addition, doing many activities increases the touristic attraction of rural tourism. It has been frequently preferred by people in recent years. Based on the importance of rural tourism, this study aims to examine the studies on Romanian rural tourism with the bibliometric analysis method. It allows to examine the characteristics of the studies such as method, technique and density. This analysis provides an opportunity to predict what the current situation of rural tourism studies is and how it will be shaped in the future. This situation reveals that the study will make an important contribution to the literature. 47 articles written in English were used as data in the study.

1. Introduction

In the last 50 years, developing technology and intensifying city life have begun to reveal different dimensions of tourism activities. The stressful and busy working life of the city life, the monotonous and constant trips to the same destinations have led to travels covering personal interests over time. In addition to the desire of people to get away from the busy areas where most of them travel and to follow their desire to travel according to their special interests, the effort to create sustainability awareness in every field throughout the world has also been effective in the change of the classical travel understanding understanding (Çamlica et al., 2022; Güneş et al., 2022). The change in consumption habits with the awareness of responsibility and sustainability has led tourism to the revitalization, development and protection of nature and natural areas. Depending on all these, countries that want to get the biggest slice of the cake created by tourism and tourism's new markets have started to work on increasing the tourism attractiveness of rural areas (Torun, 2013). The return to rural areas and nature, especially after the COVID-19 pandemic, emphasized the importance of opening these areas to tourism and increasing their attractiveness (Keane, 1992).

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Rural tourism, as the name suggests, defines visits to rural areas, visits to tourism activities such as events and festivals in rural areas. It is a type of tourism where you can get away from the noise of busy city life and enjoy the rural environment, nature and fun activities. This type of tourism, which is very popular today, not only offers people different experiences, but also takes people away from stress (Ayaz et al., 2012; Aydın & Selvi, 2012; Bran et al., 2010; Hall, 2004; Ioan et al., 2014; Kesici, 2012; Kuşat, 2014; Naghiu et al., 2005; Poruțiu et al., 2021; Sidali et al., 2011; Stoian et al., 2019; Toader et al., 2013; Tudorica, 2011; Torun, 2013; Sofică & Toader, 2013).

The aim of this study is to examine the general characteristics of the studies that emphasize the importance of rural tourism for Romania and to set an example of the direction of the future studies on rural tourism in Romania. In this respect, it is anticipated that the study will make an important contribution to Romania and the Romanian rural tourism literature.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Rural tourism

Rural tourism has become a preferred type of tourism for both those who want a healing trip and those who want to travel with a high intensity of activity, due to the fact that it is very popular and includes various activities (Bran et al., 2010; Hall, 2004; Li et al., 2010; Naghiu et al., 2005; Sidali, 2011; Toader et al., 2013; Sofică & Toader, 2013).

Kesici (2012) in a research he conducted, stated that rural tourism, which emerged with the desire of people who have lived a stressful life in city life in recent years, to go to rural areas in line with the desire to discover themselves, created a new employment opportunity for the local people. People living in the city mostly go to rural areas, visiting relatives, going for day trips. Aydın and Selvi (2012) argued that the main purpose of these visits was determined to be to get away from the oppressive and stressful city life for a while and to feel free. He stated that the concept of "rural tourism" has emerged thanks to the increase in these visits and an intense tourist flow to rural areas. Rural tourism is an industry that is constantly changing, developing and improving itself as it is wide, and that every activity to be done in this area is important because it becomes more important every day that rural tourism reaches such a wide audience. stated that it is of great importance for both local and country tourism (Ayaz et al., 2012).

Kuşat (2014) reported that rural tourism has many positive effects on the economy, social structure, cultural structure and the environment. Rural tourism does not only provide cultural exchange between tourists and local people, but also contributes to the development of the infrastructure of the region and the additional income of the local people (Torun, 2013). Among these contributions are the handicrafts of the local people. The products that are produced as a result of the long efforts and efforts of the local people are exhibited according to the local customs and

opened to the market within the scope of rural tourism activities and it is of great importance (Etikan & Çukur, 2011).

2.2. Bibliometric analysis

The word bibliometric comes from ancient Greek and is a combination of the words biblio and metric. The use of the bibliometric analysis method dates back to the 1920s. Bibliometric analysis is a widely used analysis method in the fields of management, economy and business. However, in recent years, bibliometric analysis has started to be used in the statistical analysis of content in journals and books. This analysis method is of great importance in understanding the progress of the studies carried out. In the basic sense, bibliometrics is used as a counting and statistical creation method. Bibliometric analysis can be done both quantitatively and qualitatively according to the research area (Fahimnia et al., 2015; Liu et al., 2020). Bibliometric analysis is an effective analysis method in mapping large-scale studies, identifying information gaps in research and generating new ideas for new research. When examined from this point of view, it is a guide for the scientific world in clearly revealing the current status of the studies with bibliometric analysis and thus in directing new studies (Donthu et al., 2021).

The bibliometric analysis method determines the level of use of books, journals and articles and provides great benefits in determining effective studies and authors. Bibliometric analysis method can be considered in two different types as descriptive and evaluative. Descriptive analysis method studies and examines the articles in general terms. In the evaluative analysis method, the study compiles the data on the citation numbers of the articles and is concerned with how and to what extent it affects their work (Güneş et al., 2022).

3. Methodology

In this research, thanks to the bibliometric analysis method, which is one of the content analysis methods, of the articles published about rural tourism in Romania, we reveal the development of the literature on the subject and the characteristics of the articles in question. 47 studies on rural tourism written about Romania, which has an important tourist attraction for rural tourism, were subjected to bibliometric analysis.

Studies published in English in international journals were used as data in the study. Five pieces of information were subjected to bibliometric analysis, including author density, subject, method, data collection methods, and regions determined for rural tourism. The research is limited only to the studies on rural tourism in Romania and only articles in English published in international journals.

4. Results and Discussion

In this part of the study, the bibliometric analysis results of 47 studies published in international journals and whose language is English will be included.

Table 1. Bibliometric analysis results for the studies' methods

Methods	Frequency	Percentage
Qualitative	43	91.5
Quantitative	4	8.5
Total	47	100

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 1 shows that 91.5 percent of the 47 articles randomly selected on Google Scholar were prepared qualitatively and the remaining 8.5 percent were prepared in quantitative format. There is no article prepared by the mixed method in the random selection.

Table 2. Bibliometric analysis results of the data collection techniques

Data collection technique	Frequency	Percentage
Document analysis	34	72.3
Interview	6	12.8
Survey	4	8.5
Observation	3	6.4
Total	47	100

Source: Authors' elaboration

Table 2 shows that that 91.5 of the 47 articles analyzed were made using the qualitative method, and it was concluded that the articles made using this qualitative method were mostly created with the document analysis technique with a rate of 72.3 percent. The most frequently used techniques were interview with 12.8 percent, questionnaire with 8 percent and observation with at least 6.4 percent. This shows that field studies are insufficient and studies are carried out using mostly secondary data.

Table 3. Bibliometric analysis results of the data collection techniques by regions

Region	Frequency	Percentage
Romania	40	85.1
Northwest Romania	5	10.6
Northeast Romania	5	4.3
Total	47	100

Source: Authors' elaboration

It was concluded that 85.1 percent of the 47 articles were written in the national context, while the remaining 10.6 percent were written in the Northwest Region and 4.3 percent in the Northeast Region. Rather than in-depth research on the important touristic destinations Romania has, it is seen that regional or national studies are carried out.

Table 4. Bibliometric analysis results of the studies' data sources

Data source	Frequency	Percentage
TEMPO	19	40.4
Tourism entrepreneurs	1	2.1
Local people	2	4.3
Tourists	3	6.4
Literature	14	29.8
Bank managers	1	2.1
Farmers	1	2.1
Destination	3	6.4
Tourism workers	3	6.4
Total	47	100

Source: Authors' elaboration

It was found that 40.4 percent of the data sources are based on the data obtained from the national statistical institution. It is seen that the second rank in data sources is the related literature review with a rate of 29.8 percent. When the remaining data sources are examined, it is revealed that tourism workers, destinations and tourists with a rate of 6.4 percent. In the remaining percentage, local people, farmers and bank managers took place, respectively. When the data sources are compared, it is concluded that secondary data on rural tourism is used too much and there is not enough research on host societies, destinations and tourists.

Table 5. Bibliometric analysis results of the studies' number of authors

Number of authors	Frequency	Percentage
1 author	17	36.2
2 authors	9	19.1
3 authors and more	21	47.7
Total	47	100

Source: Authors' elaboration

A percent of 47.7 of the articles consist of three or more authors, 36.2 percent have a single author and 19.1 percent have two authors. When this situation is considered in the general framework, it is seen that field studies are insufficient compared to the presence of studies with multiple authors. The fact that researches are mostly done on secondary data may cause the country to be insufficient in determining the rural tourism potential and revealing the current opportunities and threats.

Fig. 1. Cloud of words

From Fig. 1 it follows that the most frequently repeated words are “Romania”, “rural tourism”, and “sustainability”. Then, it is seen that the expressions “development”, “economic development”, “tourist expectation”, “expectation of local people”, “agritourism”, “marketing”, “globalization”, “culture”, “tradition”, “accommodation” are repeated. It has been concluded that the concepts of “Romania”, “rural tourism”, “sustainability”, “agritourism”, “globalization”, “culture”, “tradition” and “economic development” are frequently repeated in studies where qualitative research is carried out. It has been determined that the studies in which these words are used frequently are generally articles that use statistical data or are studied conceptually. It has been determined that the words that are frequently repeated in quantitative studies, which are quite few, are “expectation of tourists”, “expectation of local people”, “marketing” and “accommodation”.

5. Conclusion

When the 47 studies on the rural tourism of Romania, published in English in international journals, are examined, we see that the studies are generally qualitative and the statistical data published by TEMPO (National Institute of Statistics) or the literature study is concentrated. It has been observed that the opinions of tourists, local people, tourism representatives or experts on the subject are less sought after. It has been argued that Romania has a great potential for rural tourism, but there are very few suggestions for field research, the development of festivals or events specific to the region that can be made. There are studies that say that there are few marketing activities in order to develop Romania’s rural tourism, but it has been concluded that there is no study with local or country-wide managers who can take action on the issue.

Within the framework of the results reached at the end of the research, it is recommended to take concrete steps that can improve Romania’s rural tourism and to focus on quantitative rather than qualitative research. Another suggestion of the study is that the rich culture and traditions of the region should be emphasized in qualitative studies. The attitudes of the local people towards tourists can be

examined, and the opinions of the tourist guides can be obtained in order to develop the cultural heritage in the region.

This study deals with a bibliometric analysis of the studies written in English in the international literature about Romania's rural tourism. For future work, more Romanian studies should be taken into account by means of bibliometric analysis, examining the geographical features of the region by taking the thoughts of the local people and determining the positive and negative aspects with SWOT analysis. It is suggested that traditional festivals that can bring culture to the forefront are open to tourists and action should be taken to market rural areas with local administrators.

References

- Ayaz, N., Yeşiltaş, M., & Türkmen, F. (2012). Turizm eğitimi alan öğrencilerin kırsal turizme bakış açıları ve algıları üzerine bir araştırma. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 14(22), 103-112. <http://dergi.kmu.edu.tr/userfiles/file/haziran2012/103-112.pdf>
- Aydın, E., & Selvi, M. S. (2012). Kırsal turizm tanıtımında yerel paydaşların rolü: Arhavi örneği. *International Journal of Social and Economic Sciences*, 2(2), 133-144. <https://www.ijses.org/index.php/ijses/article/download/64/66>
- Bran, F., Hîncu, D., & Ioan, I. (2010). Potential of rural tourism in Romania. *Revista de turism – Studii și cercetări în turism*, 10, 28-31. <http://www.revistadeturism.ro/rdt/article/view/77/48>
- Etikan, S., & Çukur, T. (2011). Kırsal turizm faaliyetlerinin Çomakdağ-Kızılağaç köyü el sanatları üzerine etkisi. *Süleyman Demirel Üniversitesi Güzel Sanatlar Fakültesi Hakemli Dergisi*, 4(8), 1-15. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/193359>
- Güdü Demirbulat, Ö., & Tetik Dinç, N. (2017). Sürdürülebilir turizm konulu lisansüstü tezlerin bibliyometrik profili. *Seyahat ve Otel İşletmeciliği Dergisi*, 14(2), 20-30. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/334537>
- Hall, D. (2004). Rural tourism development in southeastern Europe: Transition and the search for sustainability. *International Journal of Tourism Research*, 6(3), 165-176. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jtr.482>
- Ioan, I., Rădulescu, C. V., & Bran, F. (2014). Romanian rural tourism: Status and prospects by innovative organizational approaches. *Revista de turism – Studii și cercetări în turism*, 17, 15-21. <http://www.revistadeturism.ro/rdt/article/view/226/179>
- Karagöz, D., & Kozak, N. (2014). Anatolia Turizm Araştırmaları Dergisi'nin bibliyometrik analizi: Araştırma konuları ve kurumlar arası iş birliğinin sosyal ağ analizi ile incelenmesi. *Türk Kütüphaneciliği*, 28(1), 47-61. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/811301>
- Kesici, M. (2012). Kırsal turizme olan talepte yöresel yiyecek ve içecek kültürünün rolü. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 14(23), 33-37. <http://dergi.kmu.edu.tr/userfiles/file/aralik2012/33-37.pdf>
- Kuşat, N. (2014). Sürdürülebilir kırsal kalkınma için bir alternatif olarak kırsal turizm ve Türkiye'de uygulanabilirliği. *Ekonomik ve Sosyal Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 10(2), 65-87. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/69479>
- Li, M., Cai, L. A., Lehto, X. Y., & Huang, J. (2010). A missing link in understanding revisit intention—The role of motivation and image. *Journal of Travel and Tourism Marketing*, 27(4), 335-348. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10548408.2010.481559>

- Naghiu, A., Vázquez, J. L., & Georgiev, I. (2005). Rural development strategies through rural tourism activities in Romania: Chance for an internal demand? *International Review on Public and Nonprofit Marketing*, 2(1), 85-95. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02893253>
- Poruțiu, A., Tirpe, O. P., Oroian, C., Mihai, V. C., Chiciudean, G. O., Chiciudean, D. I., & Poruțiu, C. (2021). Analysis on tourists' preferences for rural tourism destinations in Romania. *Societies*, 11(3), 92. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc11030092>
- Sidali, K. L., Spiller, A., & Schulze, B. (Eds.). (2011). *Food, Agri-Culture and Tourism. Linking Local Gastronomy and Rural Tourism: Interdisciplinary Perspectives*. Springer-Verlag. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/321614002>
- Sofică, A., & Toader, V. (2013). Human resource recruiting techniques in rural tourism - Cluj County, Romania. *Studia UBB Negotia*, 58(1), 61-72. <http://studia.ubbcluj.ro/download/pdf/770.pdf>
- Stoian, M., Mărcuță, A., Niculae, I., & Mărcuță, L. (2019). Analysis of Agritourism and Rural Tourism Situation in the North East of Romania. *Scientific Papers. Series "Management, Economic Engineering in Agriculture and Rural Development"*, 19(3), 535-541. http://managementjournal.usamv.ro/pdf/vol.19_3/Art70.pdf
- Şahin, S., & Acun, A. (2015). Turist rehberliği alanının bibliyometrik profili. *Balıkesir Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü Dergisi*, 18(34), 213-234. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/download/article-file/852605>
- Toader, V., Sofică, A., Petrescu, C., Negruşa, A., & Balint, C. (2013). Best practices in developing rural tourism in Cluj County, Romania. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Tourism, Transport, and Logistics* (pp. 513-517). <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/258848223>
- Torun, E. (2013). Kırsal turizmin bölge insanına katkıları. *KMÜ Sosyal ve Ekonomik Araştırmalar Dergisi*, 15(24), 31-37. <https://dergipark.org.tr/tr/download/article-file/107245>
- Tudorica, A.-V. (2011). Rural tourism in the border area Romania–Serbia. *Economics of Agriculture*, 58(1), Book 2, 352-357. <https://www.ea.bg.ac.rs/index.php/EA/article/view/789/694>